

Linking GHRM with Environmental Performance: Importance Role of Task-Related Pro-Environmental Behaviour

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 11, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : GHRM, Task-Related Pro-Environmental Behaviour, Environmental Performance, Tourism Enterprises</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4750671</p>	<p><i>There is a limited study on the link between green human resource management (GHRM), task-related pro-environmental behaviors, and environmental performance, especially in tourism enterprises. This study bridges the knowledge gap by examining the impact of GHRM on environmental performance through the mediating effect of task-related pro-environmental behaviors in tourism enterprises. For this purpose, a quantitative research methodology was used with a pre-tested instrument. To investigate the specified relationship, a purposive sampling technique was used to select 347 employees of hotels and travel agencies of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to participate in this study. We found that GHRM has a positive and significant impact on environmental performance. Furthermore, we also found that the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance is mediated by task-related pro-environmental behavior. According to the findings of the mediation analysis, task-related pro-environmental behavior. The findings have a lot of implications for tourism researchers and practitioners, especially those concerned with tourism enterprises. Study limitations and future study opportunities are also mentioned.</i></p>

Introduction

In the recent decade, policymakers, researchers, and business professionals have paid more attention to sustainability, particularly since the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals were published (UNSDGs). In this context, companies have noticed that the protection of natural resources or the environment is essential to their survival. It is reported that an organization's disregard for the natural environment would inevitably negatively impact not just its environment but also its financial sustainability (Hawken et al., 2013). Hence, Organizations have realized the importance of incorporating environmental, social, and financial sustainability into their corporate models and operations (Chaudhary, 2020). As a result, in recent years, there has been a growing interest of researchers in "greening" organizations (Chaudhary, 2020). This contains the emergence of green human resource management (GHRM) to bring environmental management into the function of Human resources management (Renwick et al., 2013). GHRM was found to be essential for the development of a sustainable culture in organizations (Kim et al., 2019).

GHRM can be described as the integration of HRM functions that significantly affect employee pro-environmental behavior and, as a result, promote an organization's proper environmental performance (Chaudhary, 2020; Bissing-olson et al., 2013). It implements environmental management in all practices of HRM, starts from recruitment and selection to training and development till employee performance management (Renwick et al., 2013). Pro-environmental behavior is a type of workplace behavior that involves all activities performed by workers to protect the environment, whether they are formal duties or efforts, such as conserving water and power, recycling paper, and printing double-sided (Chaudhary, 2020). These practices are more likely to have a positive effect on an organization's environmental performance (Chaudhary, 2020; Bissing-olson et al., 2013). Environmental performance is also dependent on sustaining employees' skills, capacities, and encouragement, basis on the environmental management system (Kim et al., 2019).

Previous studies (Chaudhary, 2020; Kim et al., 2019) have found a link between GHRM, task-related environmental behaviors among employees green, and environmental performance. However, there is a lack of studies on the interrelationships between these variables in the tourism context. GHRM, green or task-related pro-environment behavior, and environmental performance research are often focused on large enterprises, with few studies discussing these problems in small enterprises (Singh, 2020). This is particularly true for small tourism enterprises (Sobaih, 2020). Despite accounting for a significant portion of the global tourism industry,

study on GHRM, eco-friendly, green or task pro-environmental behavior, and environmental performance is still limited, with few studies addressing this issue in the small tourism context (Sobaih, 2020).

The current study contributes to this emerging phenomenon in few ways. First, in the context of Pakistan, this is the first attempt to investigate the direct impact of GHRM on environmental performance in tourism enterprises in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Second, the current research study investigation contributed to the existing literature about the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance. Last but still not least, the association between GHRM and environmental performance is enriched through possible mediator task related pro-environmental performance. The study represents a comprehensive framework based on GHRM theory (Renwick et al., 2013) and resource-based view theory (Singh, 2020) to investigate the interrelationship between GHRM and environmental performance through task-related pro-environmental behavior, which has never been studied before in tourism enterprises. The findings have important implications for tourism practitioners and scholars, especially those of tourism enterprises in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and other countries in the same region, of how to attain adequate sustainability and environmental performance using GHRM and employee task-related pro-environmental behaviors.

Relevant Literature and Theoretical Background

GHRM and Environmental Performance

Research studies on Tactical and/or high-performance both job performance and organizational performances have shown a positive and direct relationship with HRM (Sobaih et al., 2019; Becker & Gerhart 1996). Previous studies have found that employees who receive proper HRM practices, such as proper training, development, and rewards, are more likely to show proper job performance, which has an impact on overall organizational performance (Paillé, 2020). Studies in the area of environmental management have shown that GHRM has a positive and direct impact on environmental performance (Kim et al., 2019; Renwick et al., 2013; Roscoe, 2019). Particularly, GHRM has been shown to enhance employee green consciousness and green behavior, green innovativeness, and the organization's environmental performance (Chaudhary, 2020; Renwick et al., 2013; Singh, 2020). GHRM, particularly Green training and employee engagement have been shown to have a direct and significant impact on hotel environmental performance (Pham et al., 2020). GHRM also helps to increase an organization's green corporate culture and overall environmental performance (Roscoe, 2019). Studies have found that enterprises that have implemented formal environmental management systems are more likely to achieve better environmental performance (Melnik, 2003). This recognized environmental management system is composed of the policies and practices of GHRM. However, Owing to a lack of resources and HR support, small tourism businesses, such as small hotels, restaurants, and travel agents, are less likely to adopt structured HRM practices (Sobaih, 2018). Notwithstanding the environmental management of these tourism enterprises' leadership or owners/managers has still a positive impact on the environmental performance of these small businesses (Sobaih, 2020; Singh, 2020). Hence, we proposed that:

H₁: *There is a significant effect of GHRM on environmental performance in tourism enterprises.*

The mediating role of task-related pro-environmental behavior in the relation between GHRM and Environmental performance

Task-related pro-environmental behavior is a type of pro-environmental behavior which includes all positive actions by the employees directed to save natural resources or the environment and/or reduce the negative impact on the environment (Chaudhary, 2020). Employees are encouraged to engage in task-related pro-environmental behavior, whether as part of the job tasks or as voluntary acts, such as taking green initiatives when they get adequate GHRM. In a recent study conducted in the hotel industry, high-performance HRM has a positive and significant impact on employee attitudes and behaviors (Sobaih et al., 2019). Employee green behavior, i.e., organizational commitment and citizenship behaviors for the environment, was found to be significantly linked to the hotel's environmental HR management (Pham, 2020). According to the limited published study on environmental management in the tourism context, has shown that hotel employees' eco-friendly behavior has a positive, significant, and direct impact on environmental performance (Kim et al., 2019). Other studies on employee green behavior and environmental performance have been shown a significant association between employee's OCBE and environmental performance (Daily et al., 2012; Anwar et al., 2020; Pham, 2020).

The study has shown that GHRM has a direct relation with employee's task-related pro-environmental behavior and the firm's environmental strategy (Chaudhary, 2020; Singh, 2020; Pham, 2020). GHRM has also

been shown to be a predictor of employee pro-environmental practices as well as environmental performance. GHRM is also a predictor of employee pro-environmental behaviors and environmental performance (Chaudhary, 2020; Singh, 2020). A recent study investigated the role of various mediators in the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance. According to a study conducted in the hotel industry, GHRM has a positive direct impact on environmental performance as well as an indirect impact by employee engagement and eco-friendly behavior (Kim et al., 2019). Another study of large hotels found that OCBE mediates the effect of GHRM on environmental performance (Pham, 2020). Additionally, when employees are extremely satisfied with organizational engagement, they found that perceived organizational support has been shown to significantly affect individual environmental management performance (Paillé et al., 2020). According to the research study on SMEs in manufacturing sectors, found that Green innovation mediates the association between GHRM and environmental performance (Singh, 2020). A third research study on small housing enterprises found that Green innovation partially mediates the association between owner–manager green ability, incentive, and opportunity (the 3 primary aspects of GHRM) and the environmental performance of these small housing enterprises (Sobaih, 2020).

However, especially on tourism enterprises in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, no published research study has investigated the mediating role of task-related pro-environmental behaviors in the links between GHRM and environmental performance. This study makes the first attempt to investigate this association. It is expected that employee pro-environmental behaviors have a significant role in this interaction; similarly, the task-related pro-environmental behavior actions served a positive mediating effect between GHRM and environmental performance. Hence, the below hypotheses can be carried:

H₂: *There is a significant mediating effect of task-related pro-environmental behavior on GHRM in tourism enterprises.*

Figure 1: Study framework

Research Methodology

Study population and sample

For data collection, a quantitative research method was used with a survey research strategy and self-administered questionnaires. All of the research study variables were taken from well-known and widely used measures in the past. Tourism enterprises include restaurants, hotels, and travel agencies that are owned and run by their owners or independent managers with often less than 50 employees (Thomas et al., 2011). The study data was gathered from the selected participants through a survey questionnaire. To get a reasonable response rate, the questionnaire was sent in two waves. The study sent a total of 750 questionnaires to the targeted participants. Only 347 of them were returned, representing a response rate of 46%. The sample size of this study was compared favorably with similar studies on tourism enterprises (Sobaih, 2020; Singh, 2020; Chiou et al., 2011).

Instrument's measurement

The study questionnaire was derived from widely used, reliable, and validated measures in previous studies. To measure the independent variable green human resource management (GHRM), six items scale was used which was derived from (Shen & Benson 2016). To measure dependent variable environmental performance (EP), seven items scale (Yong et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2019) was used. A three items scale (Williams & Anderson

1991) was used to measure mediator task-related pro-environmental behavior (TRPEB). Scale items were categorized on a five-point Likert type scale where 1=strongly disagree, and 5= strongly agree.

Table 1: Respondent's profile

Table no 1	Hotels		Travel agencies	
<i>Participants details</i>	<i>No of participants</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>No of participants</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender				
Male	126	71.2%	133	78.2%
Female	51	28.8%	37	21.8%
Age				
21-30 Years	97	54.8%	68	40.0%
31-40	51	28.8%	49	28.8%
41-50	29	16.4%	34	20.0%
More than 50	-	-	19	11.2%
Education				
Under Matriculate	63	35.6%	52	30.6%
FA/Fsc	56	31.6%	45	26.5%
BA/Bsc	32	18.1%	29	17.1%
MA/Msc	26	14.7%	31	18.2%
Above Master	-	-	13	7.6%
Employees types				
Salary	51	28.8%	58	34.1%
Daily wages	126	71.2%	112	65.9%
<i>Total participants: N-347, (N-177 Hotels, N-170 Travel Agencies)</i>				

Table 2: Reliability Analysis

Variables names	IV/DV/MD Variables	No of items	Values of Alpha
Green Human Resource Management (GHRM)	Independent	6	.896
Environmental performance (EP)	Dependent	7	.928
Task-related pro-environmental behavior (TRPEB)	Mediator	3	.841

Table 2 shows the results of the reliability test are sufficient evidence of the instrument's reliability. As depicted the values of alpha values of all variables (GHRM, EP, and TRPEB) are above than 0.7, confirming that the scale used in the study is reliable. So, GHRM, EP, and TRPEB was measured through 6, 7, 3 items scale having Alpha values of 0.896, 0.928, and 0.841 respectively. Thus, the values of all instruments are greater than 0.7, clearly indicates that the scale used in this research is reliable.

After a good reliability results, further the study used various econometric tests to verify the content, convergent, and discriminant validity of all the constructs used in the study. The validity of the scale is not guaranteed by a good value of reliability test. As a result, all three types of validity analyses were conducted for scale validation. Through subject matter expert, instrument development experts the content validity was ensured and past studies there is no statistical analysis available to verify such validity (Hair et al., 2010). For convergent validity the study applied factor analysis. However, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used to know whether the measurement items reporting into a theoretic construct.

Table 3: KMO and BTS

Variables	GHRM (IV)	EP (DV)	TRPEB (MV)
KMO	0.609	0.788	0.711
BTS	Chi-sq<345.445>	Chi-sq <824.604>	Chi-sq <604.382>

P-value	.000(P<.05)	.000 (P<.05)	.000 (P<.05)
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Based on the values of KMO of all variables of the study is above .50 suggested that sample is appropriate. Likewise, the values of BTS are also significant for the study variables which clearly indicate that alternative hypothesis are accepted. EFA test was conducted to confirm any cross-loading issues of the scale instruments. Based on findings, the factor loading values of all scale items were above .60 (from .65 to .90).

Table 4: CFA Results

	GHRM (IV)	EP (DV)	TRPEB (MV)	
No of instruments	6	7	3	Recommended values (Hair et al., 2010)
CMIN	31.286	42.680	56.738	
DF	11	19	17	
CMIN/DF	1.79	1.85	1.82	≤ 2
RMR	.074	.059	.052	≥.05
GFI	.979	.998	.993	≥.09
AGFI	.864	.802	.836	≥.09
CFI	.988	.973	.908	≥.09
RMSEA	.40	.51	.74	≤.05

Table 5: Model summary

R	R2	Std. error	Values of Durbin Watson test
.717	.514	.750	1.8
Predictor: GHRM Dependent: EP			

Regression analysis was explained in the above table 5. As depicted that the value of R square is 0.51 which indicates that GHRM explain 51% variation in the environmental performance. The value of Durbin Watson test is almost falling in the range. Hence, DW value shows there is no issue in our research data.

Table6: coefficients

	Und. coefficient		Value of 't'	Value of 'p'
	B	Std. error		
Constant	1.195	.138	8.679	.000, <.5
GHRM	.978	.15	6.52	.000, <.5
F value: 682.46 beta value: .717				

The result of regression analysis shows that the independent variable GHRM have positive and significant relationship with dependent variable EP. High beta value of GHRM indicates that it contributes more to explain variation in the dependent variable. Hence, high value of F and significant value of p of the model shows the overall model fitness. Thus, H₀ of the current study is accepted.

Mediation Analysis

Keeping in mind Baron and Kenny's (1986) suggestion about mediating variables as that mediator's function well when independent and dependent variables have existed a strong relationship. We presume a strong association between the study predictors Green Human Resources Management with predicted variable environmental performance. The study also proposes that task-related pro-environment behavior play an important mediating role in the relationship between the variables proposed in the study.

Table 7: Mediation Results

Constructs and effects	TRPEB (Mediating variable)
GHRM (IV) → TRPEB (MV)	.908, $p = .000$
TRPEB (MV) → EP (DV)	.304, $p = .000$
Direct effect	.683, $p = .000$
Indirect effect	.276
Total effect	.959
Sobel test	$Z = 2.629, p = .000$

Table 7 shows the mediation analysis of mediator (TRPEB) on independent variable (GHRM) and dependent variable (EP) relationship. The direct effect of all the association is significant. Correspondingly, the values of z and p of the mentioned association are significant, indicating that the mediator, TRPEB, partially mediates the relationship between GHRM and EP. Hence, we received support for H_2 .

Discussion

This study was developed to address a knowledge gap in the relationship between GHRM, employee pro-environmental behaviours (task-related pro-environmental behavior), and environmental performance in tourism enterprises, particularly hotels and travel agencies in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The study started by developing a conceptual framework based on past research studies on GHRM, employee pro-environmental behaviour, and environmental performance, with a concentration on enterprises wherever applicable. Finding of the study showed that GHRM has positively influence task-related pro-environmental behavior of the employees in tourism enterprises. The result also showed that when tourism enterprises consider environmental management in the process of recruitment of the right person, offer adequate environmental training and development, reward eco-friendly behavior, and have environmental strategy, employees reacted by engaging in appropriate task-related pro-environmental behaviour. This could be clearly noticed in employee performance evaluations of environmental events of employees, roles, concerns, and policies.

Employees are more likely to become environmentally friendly and work in a team to solve any environmental problems in tourism enterprises and also tourism enterprises encourage their employees to provide suggestions and initiatives for environmental improvements. The results of current study support past studies that shown GHRM has a positively and significantly effects on employee green, eco-friendly, or task-related pro-environmental behaviours (Chaudhary, 2020; Kim et al., 2019).

Finding of the study also showed that task-related pro-environmental behaviour has significantly and positively mediates on the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance. These findings are similar to previous studies that found that employee environmental eco-friendly behaviour affects and improves environmental performance (Kim et al., 2019). The current study's findings confirm the existence in the context of tourism enterprises. However, results of several past studies, (Kim et al., 2019; Sobaih 2020; Singh 2020), this study finding revealed that GHRM has insignificant effects on environmental performance in tourism enterprises. This could be due to the fact that majority of the part-timers employees exist in tourism enterprises. Part-time employees are not a homogeneous team, according to previous studies part-time should be treated separately as compared to full-time employees in order to achieve reliable results (Sobaih et al., 2011; Sobaih 2011).

As a result, it is important that tourism enterprises pay special attention to pro-environmental behaviour (task-related pro-environmental behavior) when hiring part-time employees and invest appropriately in them. The study found that task-related pro-environmental behavior partially mediates the relationship between

GHRM and environmental performance, that enabling tourism enterprise to put a greater importance on pro-environmental behavior of their employees. This result confirms the previous research studies (Pham, 2020; Anwar et al., 2020), which found that OCBE, or pro-environmental behaviour, mediates the impact of GHRM on environmental performance. These studies, on the other hand, were carried out on large companies. This research proves this finding in the context of tourism enterprises.

Practical implications

This study provides numerous theoretical implications, especially for tourism and hospitality researchers. First, this study contributes a rich understanding to the limited studies on GHRM, employee task-related pro-environmental behavior, and environmental performance in enterprises, particularly tourism enterprises. It provides a better understanding of the interrelations between GHRM, employee pro-environmental behavior (TRPEB), and environmental performance in tourism enterprises. This study showed that GHRM has a positive and significant impact on task-related pro-environmental behavior and task-related pro-environmental behavior has a positive and significant impact on environmental performance of tourism enterprises. Second, this study confirmed the role of mediating of TRPEB in the relationship between GHRM and environmental performance in tourism enterprises. Third, the study did not find that the significant effect of GHRM on environmental efficiency in tourism enterprises. This shows that the results of the GHRM on large and small companies in another context cannot always be applied to all tourism enterprises. Thus, researchers must need to be cautious when extrapolating results to another scenario. Fourth, further attention should be needed to fully investigate and understand employee's task-related pro-environmental behavior, since it performs a fully mediating role between GHRM and environmental performance.

The study has several implications for tourism professionals, especially working in hotels and travel agencies. First, owners or managers must pay more attention to recruiting and selecting employees with pro-environmental behaviors. Personality tests are verifying these forms of behavior should be conducted before recruiting the suitable employees. This approach ensures that new candidates are compatible with the organization's environmental management policy. Second, owners and managers of tourism enterprises should be knowledgeable of their temporary workers. According to current research, the majority of employees are daily wages or casual basis. Past studies (Sobaih 2011; Sobaih et al., 2011) should consider that temporary employees are not a homogeneous group, and understanding this variability helps in the selection of the best individuals with pro-environmental behaviour that aligns with company policies, such as environmental management policy. Third, investment in in daily wages or temporary workers is urgently needed to maintain positive pro-environmental behavior. According to past study (Sobaih 2011), has shown that when temporary employees perceive a lower level of resources are more likely to react with a negative attitude and behavior. However, appropriate environmental training should be provided to newly hire employees to sustain their new positive pro-environmental behaviour.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study was conducted on tourism enterprises in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The categorization of this type of business varies from one country to another and even from one sector to another. This research study gathered data from tourism enterprises (i.e., hotels and travel agencies), for future study suggested that to collect data in another (country or industry) to validate the results of the current study. Further studies also examine the study's hypotheses in different types of tourism enterprises, such as luxury five-star hotels, as well as in a different country. Furthermore, future study could use a multi group analysis approach (Augustyn 2019; Sobaih 2021) to clearly differentiate between the results of tourism enterprises e.g., hotels and travel agencies, and moreover, the period of work experience can be employed as a moderating variable in future studies.

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